

FULL - FIELD STRAIN MEASUREMENT OF NOTCHED DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A study of macroscopic failure in discontinuous carbon fibre composites is presented, using Digital Image Correlation to monitor full-field strain within notched samples. The influences of fibre length and bundle filament count are studied for plaques produced by Directed Carbon Fibre Preforming (DCFP), which are benchmarked against a commercial semi-preg system.

Keywords: Discontinuous, random, carbon fibre, Digital Image Correlation (DIC), notch sensitivity, Directed Carbon Fibre Preforming

INTRODUCTION

Due to increasingly stringent environmental legislations imposed on the automotive industry, there is an obligation to reduce vehicle mass in order to increase fuel efficiency. The body-in-white (BIW) structure and associated closure panels typically account for around 26% of vehicle mass [1]. Carbon fibre composites are an attractive substitute for steel and aluminium, with their high specific properties enabling a 40-60% weight saving. Historically, applications of carbon composites have been restricted to aerospace and motor sport applications, because wider usage has been prevented by long cycle times (>4hrs), high material costs and labour intensive processing. However, recent developments in discontinuous carbon fibre composites [2, 3] have demonstrated that it is now feasible to produce cost-effective semi-structural and structural components for medium volume applications (1,000-20,000ppa).

Directed Carbon Fibre Preforming (DCFP) is an automated process for producing discontinuous fibre preforms for liquid moulding [4, 5]. A robot-mounted mechanical chopper head sprays fibres and a polymeric binder on to a perforated tool. The cavity behind the perforated tool is evacuated, which holds the deposited fibres in place as the thickness of the laminate is built up. After spraying, a matched perforated tool is lowered to compress the preform to control its thickness and to consolidate it using circulating hot air. The process displays numerous advantages over other preforming techniques: Touch labour is minimal and material costs are 75% lower than a typical commercial prepreg material [6], because fibres are used in their cheapest roving-tow

form without any intermediate processing and with little wastage (<3%) [7]. Cycle times are typically 5-10 minutes for complex 3D shapes.

Previous work has shown that optimum in-plane properties for thin (<3mm) DCFP closure panels are obtained using short 6mm, filamentised 24K bundles [2]. Filamentisation is a method for fragmenting large tows into smaller bundles to achieve uniform preform coverage, whilst exploiting the financial benefits of using high filament counts [2]. There is an increased natural tendency for the tow to fragment when cut shorter, hence filament count is proportional to fibre length. Shorter, filamentised bundles provide superior part coverage and fibre coverage homogeneity and also provide greater control over fibre placement around tight radii on the tool. Their use however, raises concern regarding notch sensitivity because of poor crack bridging and small damage zone characteristics [8] in comparison to a long fibre, high filament count variant. Notch sensitivity is of particular importance in the automotive industry for closure panels, because they are often fastened to the main BIW using bolts or contain features which act as stress raising discontinuities in the panel.

The onset of notch sensitivity is defined to occur when the notched specimen strength falls to 85% of an unnotched reference specimen [9], for specimens with increasing hole size. Lindhagen and Berglund [9] used an analytical model to establish the magnitude of the notch required to observe the onset of notch sensitivity. The threshold diameter was found to be much larger than experimentally tested, in the order of 30-140mm. Hitchen *et al.* [10] found that the notch sensitivity of random carbon fibre laminates was independent of fibre length (1, 5, 15mm), but dependent on the notch curvature/diameter (\varnothing 1-10mm). Random materials with long (25mm) or continuous (CFRM) fibres exhibited a low sensitivity to notches for notch diameters in the range of 2-15mm [8, 11]. Recently, Feraboli *et al.* [3] also found that long fibre (50mm) random plaques were notch insensitive, due to internal stress concentrations arising from the heterogeneous nature of the material. This was used to explain the tendency of the material to fail away from the notch, particularly for small hole sizes (3-6mm).

This study aims to investigate the notch sensitivity of random discontinuous fibre DCFP materials, compared with a commercial automotive body panel system containing woven fibres. Four DCFP material permutations are studied, including two fibre lengths and two bundle sizes (by induced bundle fragmentation). Tensile specimens of increasing width, containing a central hole, are used to establish the onset of notch sensitivity, by comparing the ultimate strengths against an unnotched benchmark. A Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system is used to produce full-field strain distributions in notched specimens, to determine strain concentration factors within the vicinity of the notch and in local areas of high strain. This detailed information is used to explain the various failure initiation and propagation mechanisms observed experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimen Manufacture

Methodology outlined by Lindhagen and Berglund [9] was followed in order to determine the notch sensitivity of the DCFP and semi-preg materials. Circular notches of $\text{Ø}9.5\text{mm}$ to $\text{Ø}30\text{mm}$ were tested in straight-sided tensile specimens, whilst maintaining a constant diameter-to-width ratio of 3:8. A standard 25mm wide tensile specimen was used as a benchmark in each case and notched specimens were cut to the same 250mm gauge length but with increasing widths (25, 40, 60 and 80mm). The notch sensitivity results were assumed to be independent of specimen length, since the gauge length was over three times longer than the largest width and ten times longer than the fibre length. Five materials were tested during this work as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 - Notch sensitivity testing materials test matrix.

	Material	V_f	Fibre Length	Fibre Arrangement
1	DCFP 1	30%	23mm	Non-filamentised random
2	DCFP 2	30%	6mm	Non-filamentised random
3	DCFP 3	30%	23mm	Filamentised random
4	DCFP 4	30%	6mm	Filamentised random
5	Semi-preg	-	Continuous	0/90° woven

DCFP plaques were manufactured with a fibre volume fraction of 30%, using two fibre lengths available on the current chopper gun installation. Toho Tenax 24K STS carbon fibre bundles were used, both in their natural state (non-filamentised) and with the highest level of induced filamentisation possible (see for details [2]). Semi-preg consisted of two 600gsm woven plies sandwiched about a low density syntactic core. A fine woven glass reinforced film was used to enhance the surface finish of the plaque.

Tensile Testing

Specimens were loaded to failure in a 2-grip hydraulic Instron 500 tension/compression machine, at an extension rate of 1.0 mm/min. A sampling rate of 1Hz was adopted for the load data acquisition. A Limes Vic3D Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system was used to produce full-field strain measurements of the experimental tensile specimens. The surface of each sample was sprayed white and then a black speckle pattern was applied to obtain a randomised grey level distribution. Both layers of paint were applied using a Harder and Steenbeck Evolution Airbrush, with a $\text{Ø}0.4\text{mm}$ splatter nozzle. Efforts were made to ensure that the diameter of the speckles were as uniform and small as possible to provide a good spatial resolution.

A white light (6400K colour temperature) was used to illuminate the area of interest. Images of the specimen surface were recorded throughout the test at an acquisition rate of 0.33 Hz, via two 5.0 Megapixel CCD cameras fitted with Pentax C37500 lenses ($f = 75\text{mm}$, 1:2.8 D). The cameras were mounted on a tripod positioned 1.5m away from the subject to provide a $120 \times 120\text{mm}$ field of view. The local displacement resolution of the system is 0.01pixels, which corresponds to $0.24\mu\text{m}$ for the current set up. An image processing unit was used to calculate a three-dimensional displacement field, based on correlation calculations. The method consists of correlating the grey pixels in each deformed image to the counterpart in the undeformed (reference) image. The area of interest of each image was divided into small square subsets of size 25×25 pixels, using a step size of 3 pixels (i.e. correlation was only performed on every third pixel in the x and y directions). Images were recorded in Limes VicSnap, in preparation for post processing analysis in Limes Vic3D.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the absolute strength values for the five materials tested (calculated using net cross sectional area). The highly filamentised short fibre DCFP 4 exhibited the highest unnotched strength (207MPa) and the non-filamentised DCFP 1 and DCFP 2 exhibited the lowest ($\sim 60\text{MPa}$). The unnotched tensile strength of the semi-preg was closely matched by DCFP 3 at approximately 130MPa. However, the strength of the semi-preg falls to the same level as DCFP 1 once a notch is introduced. Figure 1 indicates that the notch sensitivity of the DCFP material is largely dominated by the bundle size rather than the fibre lengths tested. The reductions in strength for DCFP 1 and DCFP 2 are negligible compared with the reductions for DCFP 4 when notches are introduced.

Figure 1 - Notch sensitivity results for four DCFP plaques and one semi-preg plaque. The DCFP plaques are distinguished by fibre length (long (23mm) or short (6mm)) and level of induced filamentisation (high or low).

Relative strength retentions are plotted in Figure 2 for increasing notch diameters. All strength values have been normalised with respect to the strength of the un-notched reference specimens. DCFP 1 (non filamentised / long fibre) was seen to be insensitive to the notch sizes tested. No significant reduction in strength is observed for any of the hole diameters and the small fluctuations about the 100% mark can be attributed to experimental variation, reported in the form of standard deviation bars in Figure 1. DCFP 3 (filamentised / long fibre) is the second most insensitive material since it crosses the 85% notch sensitivity threshold at a diameter of 15mm. DCFP 2 crosses the 85% threshold at Ø8.5mm and finally DCFP 4 and the semi-preg are the most notch sensitive systems, both crossing the threshold at approximately Ø3.5mm for the range of hole sizes tested. Although the highly filamentised, short fibre DCFP 4 is more sensitive to circular notches than a bundled material, the notch sensitivity characteristics are still comparable to a woven 0/90° semi-preg. Furthermore, the ultimate strength of DCFP 4 is approximately 50% higher than the semi-preg for each notch size (see Figure 1).

Figure 2 - Notched strength normalised with respect to the un-notched strength for the four DCFP plaques and one semi-preg plaque. (Dotted line represents the 85% notch sensitivity threshold as discussed in [9])

Failure of the Semi-preg and DCFP 4 occurred in the notched net section for every sample. Non filamentised bundles with longer fibre lengths resulted in failures occurring randomly along the gauge length of each sample in either the net or gross section. Over 50% of the samples for DCFP 1 failed in the gross section area, for all hole sizes considered. Figure 3 shows the damage initiation and propagation for a selection of tensile samples for Semi-preg, DCFP 1 and DCFP 4. The DIC strain plots for DCFP 1 shows an example of a specimen where failure occurred in the gross section.

Longer fibres in high filament count tow form exhibit much better fracture toughness properties than short single filaments. This was previously reported in [8] for the notch sensitivity of GMT materials and in [12] for glass-based SMCs. The authors in [13] identify the damage mechanisms relating to different random fibre architectures, with a specific emphasis on damage zone creation. The relative size of the damage zone varies for bundled and filamentised materials, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Damage can either initiate in highly stressed regions or at local concentrations at bundle ends, depending on the composition of the material.

Two potential failure initiation mechanisms can be identified for the non-filamentised DCFP 1 material. Fibre bundles orientated transversely to the load, as shown in Figure 4 (iii), and stress concentrations at bundle ends. These occur due to the large local gradient in elastic properties between the bundle and the surrounding matrix. For damage sensitive architectures, local heterogeneity can lead to larger stress concentrations than those present at the notch (for an isotropic material with $d/w=0.375$, $K_t=2.26$). Cracks form at these sites, which then propagate along bundle boundaries to create a large damage zone, which may or may not coincide with the notch. Figure 3 (iii) shows the full-field strain for the DCFP 1 sample and it can be clearly seen that region 'A' experiences greater strain than the region that surrounds the notch. Figure 4 (iii) highlights the fact that numerous fibre ends can be found in the region where final failure occurs, thus providing an initiation point for the failure not coinciding with the stress raiser at the notch. Final failure of the DCFP materials is governed by fracture or pull-out of longitudinal fibres in the loading direction. This mechanism is dependent on the fibre critical length, which is governed by the bundle filament count and fibre length [14].

For the short fibre, highly filamentised DCFP 4 sample the strain distribution is initially more uniform than for the long fibre bundled material. As the strain increases, multiple damage zones are formed, but the presence of the notch concentration overwhelms the material induced concentrations and the damage zone and crack form near to the equator of the hole. Woven materials are generally macroscopically homogeneous (Figure 3 (i)) and therefore damage initiates at the stress concentration, due to the geometry of the sample, at the notch tip. The stress raiser at the notch concentrates the damage zone, which remains to be very small in the absence of off-axis fibres. Final failure is catastrophic, as the longitudinal fibres reach their failure strength and fracture at the equator of the notch, as shown in Figure 4 (i).

Figure 3 – Example of DIC full-field strain plots (i) Semi-preg (ii) Short fibre, filamentised – DCFP 4 and (iii) Long fibre, non-filamentised– DCFP 1

Scale indicates the normalised local strain in each specimen. Percentage underneath denotes global strain of the sample.

A strain concentration factor approach is presented in the current work to quantify the level of material heterogeneity. Using results from DIC, regions of strain concentration have been identified and the average strain across that region measured (see Figure 5). By utilising this approach, strain concentration factors (K_t) in the region of the notch and in regions of material inhomogeneity are determined. For example, in the long fibre sample (DCFP 1) an alternative region (denoted region C in Figure 5) exhibits high levels of strain. The K_t values obtained from this study are presented in Table 2, for the three samples in Figure 3 at the second strain level. It can be seen that discontinuities in the inhomogeneous material resulted in a strain concentration factor of three times the magnitude of that near the notch. The transverse bundle causing failure can be seen at the point of failure in that region, see Figure 4 (iii), as well as numerous fibre ends.

Figure 4 – Failure of (i) Semi-preg (ii) Short Fibre – DCFP 4 (iii) Long Fibre – DCFP 1

Figure 5 - Diagram to show nominal strain (A), peak strain (C) and the strain in the notched region (B)

Table 2 - Strain Concentration Factors, K_t

Material	Semi-preg	DCFP 1	DCFP 4	Theoretical isotropic homogeneous material
K_t	2.214	1.403 (notch) 3.948 (region A)	3.068	2.26

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that short, highly filamentised composite materials provide a greater ultimate strength in notched samples when compared to long fibre, non-filamentised samples (DCFP 1). Interestingly, they also have greater notch strength when compared to woven fabric composite materials. Short fibre composites (DCFP 2 and DCFP 4) show poorer strength retention when compared to long, non-filamentised fibres such as DCFP 1 as the size of the notch is increased within test samples. DCFP 4 and semi-preg materials show highly notch sensitive behaviour as the notch size is increased, but the macroscopic response of long, non-filamentised fibres (DCFP 1) is virtually notch insensitive as it retains over 85% of its original strength even at a hole diameter of $\text{\O}30\text{mm}$, for the range of hole sizes tested.

The use of DIC has allowed regions of high strain to be identified during tensile testing. DIC has allowed the progression of damage to be tracked across the specimen and has assisted with the identification of mesoscopic failure modes. Short fibre composites were shown to suffer damage around the notch region, and the crack progression in these is irregular as the cracks bridge the gap between the notch and the edge of the sample. The long fibre composites (DCFP 1) suffer damage away from the notch region, and initiates at the point where numerous fibre ends are present. The crack progression in the long fibre composite is even more irregular as the cracks follows the path of the fibres, as the fibres ultimately pull-out of the sample.

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